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Lead Author(s):	V. Subramaniam Rajkumar (TUD)
Co-author(s):	E. Widl (AIT), M.C Pham (CEA), J. Nikolettatos (CRES), O. Gehrke (DTU), S. Giuseppe, G. Paludetto (RSE), A.G. Acosta (RWTH), P. Raussi (VTT)
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List of Abbreviations

AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
DMA	Direct Memory Access
GDRTS	Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulation
GNU	GNU's Not Unix!
HIL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
IP	Intellectual Property
JaNDER	Joint Test Facility for Smart Energy Networks with Distributed Energy Resources
JAR	Java Archive
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
MQTT	Message Queue Telemetry Transport
PC	Personal Computer
RI	Research Infrastructure
REST	Representational State Transfer
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
uAPI	Universal Application Programming Interface
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
VILLAS	Virtually Interconnected Laboratories for LARge systems Simulation/emulation

Executive Summary

One of the key objectives of the ERIGrid 2.0 project is the virtual integration of geographically distributed Research Infrastructures to realise the vision of a joint virtual Research Infrastructure. Towards this end, this work focused on developing laboratory-based middleware and data exchange as a service, respectively. The middleware is a set of shared software tools and services to seamlessly integrate Research Infrastructure (RI)s, such as transport protocols, interface semantics, etc. This document presents the summary of the work undertaken in the two tasks, more specially:

- Software development of a simplified and standardised interface, i.e., Universal Application Programming Interface. The Universal Application Programming Interface eliminates the need for users to understand the diverse details of each individual Research Infrastructure, by providing a tool-agnostic interface for accessing and interacting with other Research Infrastructures. It has been designed to support various applications, such as co-simulation and distributed laboratory experiments. The Universal Application Programming Interface is an integral part of the middleware and seeks to simplify the process of joint multi-RI experiments.
- Proof-of-concept of data exchange between multiple Research Infrastructures as a service using the developed Universal Application Programming Interface. This demonstration shows how the chosen middleware development covers the required services for data exchange.

This document also provides example documentation for the developed software tools with links to the respective code repositories to enable Research Infrastructure integration.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document presents a summary of the work undertaken focused on the development of distributed laboratory middleware to improve and extend well-established laboratory coupling frameworks such as Virtually Interconnected Laboratories for LArge systems Simulation/emulation (VILLAS)¹, Joint Test Facility for Smart Energy Networks with Distributed Energy Resources (JaNDER)², or LabLink³ developed outside of ERIGrid 2.0 by some of the project partners. The major focus is on the development and application of an Universal Application Programming Interface (uAPI) which serves as a tool-agnostic service for data exchange in multi-Research Infrastructure (RI) experiments.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 2 provides the motivation behind the middleware development. The development of the uAPI is covered in Section 3 along with its advantages and limitations and conclusions are provided in Section 4.

¹<https://www.fein-aachen.org/en/projects/villas-framework/>

²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4317872>

³<https://github.com/AIT-Lablink>

2 Motivation for a Laboratory Middleware

This section discusses the motivation behind the development of the distributed laboratory middleware in ERIGrid 2.0. First, based on experiences from ERIGrid, challenges in joint experiments are identified in Section 2.1. Subsequently, an overview of existing laboratory coupling tools is provided in Section 2.2, followed by the proposed middleware design and architecture in Section 2.3.

2.1 Lessons Learned from ERIGrid

Some of the existing laboratory coupling tools, mainly JaNDER, were used in the predecessor project ERIGrid⁴, and several lessons were learned from it. These lessons have informed the development of the laboratory middleware in ERIGrid 2.0. In the following, the lessons learned are summarised (Strasser et al., 2017; Palensky, van der Meer, Lopez, Joseph, & Pan, 2017; Pellegrino et al., 2020).

- *Naming convention:* ERIGrid developed a naming convention for the data exchange between laboratories for geographically distributed experiments. While very exact, the naming convention results in very long names for data signals. Since there was no automated way of attaching the names of the data signals, this was done manually for each and every signal. In practice, the long names turned users away from them and caused various partners and people to use short-cut names, which resulted in a lot of additional manual labour to always change and update the short-cut names based on which partners are participating in the experiment.
- *Units and scaling:* Another lesson learned is on the magnitude of the units depending on the lab; for instance, power could be expressed as kW or W. This variability between the units resulted in laboratories needing to separately confirm and manually update their programs to accept units of the specific magnitude to avoid a mix-up in control signals depending on the magnitude.
- *Local RI differences:* In the ERIGrid demonstration action, which was a geographically distributed experiment, real-time simulators of two different partners were used and the implementation of the interconnection between the laboratories was organised in a slightly different manner and with different parameter names. These slight changes meant that each time the partner operating the real-time simulator changed, also the signal magnitude information and names of the signals needed to be updated manually.

2.2 Existing Lab Coupling Tools

In this section, three of the existing laboratory coupling tools, i.e., VILLASframework, JaNDER, and Lablink are discussed.

2.2.1 VILLASframework

The *VILLASframework* is a tool-set for local and Geographically Distributed Real-Time Simulation (GDRTS). It is actively developed by the Institute for Automation of Complex Power

⁴<https://erigrd.eu>

2.2.2 JaNDER

JaNDER is a communication platform developed within the ERIGrid project that allows data to be exchanged between different RIs. The main features of this platform are the secure connection using Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS), simplicity of installation, and modularity. JaNDER's core functionality is the replication of infrastructure data through a cloud node. When data is recorded in a local database, it is mirrored in the cloud database and vice versa. At this level, the data is simply transported without any interpretation of its structure. The building blocks of JaNDER are shown in Figure 2 and described below:

- *Cloud Node*: Redis database⁵ in the cloud, serving as a platform for exchanging data between the various RI nodes. Access to the cloud node is secured using certificates and HTTPS protocol. It acts as the intermediary between the local nodes of the different RI instances.
- *RI Database*: A Redis database located at the facility that serves as the endpoint for data read and write operations. The replication software, if running, synchronises the data between the cloud and local nodes.
- *Replication Software*: Developed in Golang⁶, the software opens connections to both the local Redis node and the cloud node using secure certificates. It replicates data between the two nodes by subscribing to the Redis keyspace notifications and intercepting updates of keys matching a specific pattern. The replication can be conducted bidirectionally between local and remote nodes.

Figure 2: JaNDER transport equipped with universal API, each RI is equipped with a local database instance connected to the cloud node.

⁵<https://redis.io>

⁶<https://go.dev>

Built on top of the replication software, a layer defining the data model for the exchanged measurements can be constructed. This layer makes data accessible to the user and maps the model class instances to the appropriate database data structures that need to be replicated like the universal API. At present, the implementation of the APIs enables the use of channels, samples, and events. The current implementation of the API enables JaNDER to operate in various infrastructures, with compatibility and interaction with different transport services still under development.

2.2.3 Lablink

Lablink, developed by AIT, is a tool that aims to make laboratory development and evaluation more efficient, flexible, and modular. It serves as a communication protocol that is tailored to meet the specific needs of Controller HIL or HIL simulation systems used in contemporary laboratories.

Lablink is centred around a middleware platform, known as Lablink Core, which handles communication between distributed clients. This middleware provides facilities for data routing and encoding and is implemented as a distributed application. It exposes interfaces that allow Lablink's functionality to be accessed, forming the foundation for developing dedicated Lablink clients that can access shared components such as laboratory hardware or simulation tools. Additionally, it is possible to build utility tools, such as client synchronisation or data logging, on top of Lablink Core's core infrastructure.

Lablink's primary element offers a communication system that employs MQTT as its transport protocol. It facilitates both asynchronous messaging and synchronous remote procedure calls. Moreover, the Lablink core features several client services. Presently, the Lablink core is developed as a Java library. The source code on the Lablink Core code can be found in an online repository, while the relevant packages are downloadable as Java Archive (JAR) files through the dedicated remote Maven repository.

Lablink's architecture is shown in Figure 3 and described below:

- *Lablink Clients*: A Lablink client is a self-contained program that establishes a solitary link with the Lablink system and can serve various functions. One function is acting as a bridge between other Lablink clients and an external simulator, such as DIgSILENT PowerFactory, to facilitate data exchange. Another function is serving as a connector to a laboratory hardware device using predefined communication standards, such as Modbus Transmission Control Protocol (TCP) or a serial interface. Lastly, a Lablink client can function as an independent software process that integrates both the logic and the Lablink connection.
- *MQTT Broker*: Lablink relies on MQTT as its underlying communication protocol, which necessitates the use of an MQTT broker to disseminate messages between Lablink clients. MQTT offers several features that are shared with Lablink. For instance, it allows for secure connections, and a client can configure Secure Sockets Layer (SSL)-secured communication with the broker. Additionally, load distribution of the MQTT broker is another useful feature, and various open-source MQTT brokers are available that implement this capability.
- *Lablink Connection*: The Lablink connection is an integral component of the core library and serves as an application interface for accessing the Lablink system. Each Lablink client utilises a single Lablink connection, which facilitates the sending of messages and

remote procedure calls via MQTT to other Lablink clients. The Lablink connection interface provides a means to accomplish this.

Figure 3: Overview of the Lablink architecture.

2.3 Towards an Integration Approach

The main objective of the proposed middleware is to enable seamless data exchange between different RIs such as physical laboratories, real-time simulators, and non real-time simulators. Although there are various ongoing development projects that partially cover the intended scope, such as VILLASframework, JaNDER, and Lablink, none of them offers a one-size-fits-all solution for all of the needs in ERIGrid 2.0. Hence, keeping these facts in mind, the middleware design and development focused on the following two core aspects:

- Continuing the development of approaches geared towards “getting data from RI1 to RI2”, these can be seen as interchangeable “transport modules”, which can be chosen depending on the requirements of a particular test case, and
- Creating a general software framework aimed at making the transport modules easier to use, amend their functionality, and prevent work duplication.

To this end, a general software architecture as shown in Figure 4 was designed. In particular, the middleware provides the following functionality:

- *Universal Application Programming Interface (uAPI)*: A transport-independent abstraction layer, which makes usage of multiple transports possible. Hence, the time and effort in having to implement an individual laboratory-to-transport interface are eliminated.
- *Harmonised Functionality*: The uAPI also provides common core functionality, such as getting a list of available signals, RIs, status, etc.

The subsequent section describes the uAPI in greater detail.

Figure 4: Overview of the ERIGrid 2.0 laboratory middleware architecture.

3 Development of an uAPI for Data Exchange

This section discusses the software development of the uAPI and motivates its design choices. In particular, as part of the lab middleware, the uAPI realises interoperability services and service discoverability.

3.1 Software Development

The uAPI was designed, keeping in mind the need for ease of usage and adoption. To this end, it was developed as a Representational State Transfer (REST) API. It is an architectural style that defines a set of constraints for creating web services. REST API is a web service that exposes a set of endpoints or Uniform Resource Locators (URLs) to perform operations over Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP)/HTTPS. These endpoints typically map to resources or objects in a system, such as a database, and the HTTP verbs (i.e., GET, POST, PUT, DELETE) are used to perform operations on those resources. The main reason for choosing the REST API was the following:

- Stateless behaviour, meaning that the server does not maintain any state about the client's requests. Instead, each request contains all the necessary information for the server to process it. This makes REST APIs highly scalable and easy to cache.
- Simplicity and compatibility with a wide range of platforms and programming languages.
- Ease of implementation with limited to no software development knowledge necessary.

Hence, the uAPI provides a set of common functionality, such as getting signals, sending control commands, etc., irrespective of the type of lab coupling tool used. Therefore, conducting multi-RI experiments is made potentially easier.

3.2 Implementation

The implementation of the uAPI is currently supported by the three transport tools, discussed in Section 2.2. This consists of the following components, at the very least:

- *Server*: An HTTP server implementing the uAPI which is accessed by the clients.
- *Client*: An HTTP client implementing the uAPI which makes requests towards a compatible server.
- *Transport*: External tool to facilitate data exchange between RIs. Examples of current implementations are VILLASframework, JaNDER, or LabLink.
- *Node*: A software instance of the transport solution typically deployed in each RI. For example, a virtual machine or dedicated Personal Computer (PC).
- *RI Adapter*: RI-specific data-exchange software client between the RI Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA)/laboratroy the uAPI server.

This data exchange and flow is better visualised through Figure 5. As can be seen the RI adapter acts as the client between the uAPI server and the laboratroy/SCADA of RI1 for data exchange. It places standard HTTP requests such as GET, POST, PUT, DELETE, etc. A similar

setup is assumed to exist in RI2. Thus, with such a setup, multiple transports can be seamlessly used for different multi-RI experiments, depending on the specific application and use case.

Figure 5: Example implementation of the uAPI between two RIs.

3.2.1 Implementation in VILLASnode

An example implementation of the uAPI for the VILLASnode is described below. A similar implementation is carried out in JaNDER and Lablink. VILLASnode has its own API based on the libwebsockets⁷ library. Furthermore, like the uAPI, it has been developed following the OpenAPI⁸ specification. Based on this experience, the uAPI implementation of VILLASnode was developed. It is implemented as a new node type, which is defined in a VILLASnode configuration file. The node's documentation⁹ provides additional details. The root entry point of the uAPI implementation relates to the one of the VILLASnode API by appending the `/universal/api_node` to the URL. For example, for the server `www.example.com`, the VILLASnode API root endpoint is `www.example.com/api/v2`, while the root endpoint for the uAPI is `www.example.com/api/v2/universal/api`.

⁷<https://libwebsockets.org/>

⁸<https://www.openapis.org/>

⁹<https://villas.fein-aachen.org/docs/node/nodes/api/>

Testing Results

Below, the outcomes of various tests are shown.

- *Get API info*

```
[villas@f6ce2e5728f4 VILLASnode]$ curl -v http://localhost:8080/api/v2/universal/api_node/info
* Trying 127.0.0.1:8080...
* Connected to localhost (127.0.0.1) port 8080 (#0)
> GET /api/v2/universal/api_node/info HTTP/1.1
> Host: localhost:8080
> User-Agent: curl/7.82.0
> Accept: */*
>
* Mark bundle as not supporting multiuse
< HTTP/1.1 200 OK
< content-type: application/json
< content-length: 200
< Access-Control-Allow-Headers: Content-Type
< Access-Control-Allow-Methods: GET, POST, OPTIONS
< Access-Control-Allow-Origin: *
< Access-Control-Max-Age: 86400
< Server: VILLASnode (v0.11.0-37c9efa-release)
<
{
  "id": "api_node",
  "uuid": "1d9e47bc-91e6-7bb0-a8a2-e623b43ec35b",
  "transport": {
    "type": "villas",
    "version": "0.11.0",
    "build": "v0.11.0-37c9efa-release"
  }
}
* Connection #0 to host localhost left intact
```

Figure 6: Get API info response.

- *Get transport status*

```
[villas@f6ce2e5728f4 VILLASnode]$ curl -v http://localhost:8080/api/v2/universal/api_node/status
* Trying 127.0.0.1:8080...
* Connected to localhost (127.0.0.1) port 8080 (#0)
> GET /api/v2/universal/api_node/status HTTP/1.1
> Host: localhost:8080
> User-Agent: curl/7.82.0
> Accept: */*
>
* Mark bundle as not supporting multiuse
< HTTP/1.1 200 OK
< content-type: application/json
< content-length: 30
< Access-Control-Allow-Headers: Content-Type
< Access-Control-Allow-Methods: GET, POST, OPTIONS
< Access-Control-Allow-Origin: *
< Access-Control-Max-Age: 86400
< Server: VILLASnode (v0.11.0-37c9efa-release)
<
{
  "connected": "unknown"
}
* Connection #0 to host localhost left intact
```

Figure 7: Get transport status response.

- *Get channels*

```

• [villas@f6ce2e5728f4 VILLASnode]$ curl -v http://localhost:8080/api/v2/universal/api_node/channels
* Trying 127.0.0.1:8080...
* Connected to localhost (127.0.0.1) port 8080 (#0)
> GET /api/v2/universal/api_node/channels HTTP/1.1
> Host: localhost:8080
> User-Agent: curl/7.82.0
> Accept: */*
>
* Mark bundle as not supporting multiuse
< HTTP/1.1 200 OK
< content-type: application/json
< content-length: 1302
< Access-Control-Allow-Headers: Content-Type
< Access-Control-Allow-Methods: GET, POST, OPTIONS
< Access-Control-Allow-Origin: *
< Access-Control-Max-Age: 86400
< Server: VILLASnode (v0.11.0-37c9efa-debug)
<
[
  {
    "id": "random",
    "datatype": "float",
    "readable": true,
    "writable": false,
    "description": "Signal 1",
    "rate": 100.0,
    "payload": "samples"
  },

```

Figure 8: Get channels response (the entire response is not shown).

- *Channel sample (GET)*

```

• [[villas@f6ce2e5728f4 VILLASnode]$ curl -v http://localhost:8080/api/v2/universal/api_node/channel/random/sample
* Trying 127.0.0.1:8080...
* Connected to localhost (127.0.0.1) port 8080 (#0)
> GET /api/v2/universal/api_node/channel/random/sample HTTP/1.1
> Host: localhost:8080
> User-Agent: curl/7.82.0
> Accept: */*
>
* Mark bundle as not supporting multiuse
< HTTP/1.1 200 OK
< content-type: application/json
< content-length: 154
< Access-Control-Allow-Headers: Content-Type
< Access-Control-Allow-Methods: GET, POST, OPTIONS
< Access-Control-Allow-Origin: *
< Access-Control-Max-Age: 86400
< Server: VILLASnode (v0.11.0-37c9efa-debug)
<
{
  "timestamp": 1683553687.6822593,
  "value": 0.32770909871158244,
  "validity": "unknown",
  "source": "unknown",
  "timesource": "unknown"
}
* Connection #0 to host localhost left intact

```

Figure 9: Channel sample (GET) response.

- Channel sample (PUT)

```

• [villas@f6ce2e5728f4 VILLASnode]$curl -v -XPUT -d '{"timestamp": 1648482084.1462665,"value":1234.0}'
* Trying 127.0.0.1:8080...
* Connected to localhost (127.0.0.1) port 8080 (#0)
> PUT /api/v2/universal/api_node/channel/sig1_in/sample HTTP/1.1
> Host: localhost:8080
> User-Agent: curl/7.82.0
> Accept: */*
> Content-Length: 48
> Content-Type: application/x-www-form-urlencoded
>
* Mark bundle as not supporting multiuse
< HTTP/1.1 200 OK
< content-type: application/json
< content-length: 2
< Access-Control-Allow-Headers: Content-Type
< Access-Control-Allow-Methods: GET, POST, OPTIONS
< Access-Control-Allow-Origin: *
< Access-Control-Max-Age: 86400
< Server: VILLASnode (v0.11.0-37c9efa-debug)
<
* Connection #0 to host localhost left intact

```

Figure 10: Channel sample (PUT) response.

3.3 Proof-of-Concept for Data Exchange

The uAPI has been applied for a proof-of-concept for data exchange using different tools and RIs. The tests involved exchanging simple variables and measurements using three previously discussed lab-coupling tools VILLASframework, JaNDER, and Lablink. The tests were conducted between the following RIs:

- *RWTH (Germany)* \longleftrightarrow *DTU (Denmark)*: The test exchanged data between DTU's Syslab and RWTH's real-time grid simulator using the VILLASframework.
- *TUD (Netherlands) and VTT (Finland)* \longleftrightarrow *RSE (Italy)*: The test exchanged data between RSE's lab and TUD's real-time grid simulator using JaNDER and the uAPI. This is better illustrated through Figure 11 which shows the creation of the local Redis instance and channels using the uAPI. A similar test was carried out between VTT and RSE.

```

2023/05/03 07:49:59.140283 Replicating local Redis instance to remote address: https://ec2-54-72-205-227.eu-west-1.compute.amazonaws.com/redis
2023/05/03 07:49:58.140472 Subscribing for remote changes to the namespace: demo4
create redis client, connection with localhost:6379
Server running
Redis localhost:6379 connected!
2023/05/03 07:50:29.534899 Replicating local Redis instance to remote address: https://ec2-54-72-205-227.eu-west-1.compute.amazonaws.com/redis
2023/05/03 07:50:29.534984 Subscribing for remote changes to the namespace: demo4
create redis client, connection with localhost:6379
Server running
Redis localhost:6379 connected!
get channels
2023/05/03 07:53:08.495931 (remote)→(local) hash demo4:channelId:RSE::CHP:ME:Watt.instMsg1 entries 9
get channels
2023/05/03 07:54:48.295384 (local)→(remote) hash demo4:channelId:FloatTest entries 9
channel written
get channels
2023/05/03 07:55:35.597279 (local)→(remote) hash demo4:channelId:FloatTest entries 9
channel written

```

Figure 11: Data exchange between TUD and RSE using JaNDER and uAPI.

- *TUD (Netherlands)* \longleftrightarrow *AIT (Austria)*: Data was exchanged between these two RIs using Lablink and the uAPI.

All the geographical RI locations and data exchanges are depicted in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Proof-of-concept for data exchange using the ERIGrid 2.0 uAPI and middleware.

3.4 OpenAPI Documentation

The uAPI is designed as per the OpenAPI specification⁸ which seeks to standardise HTTP APIs. The OpenAPI specification defines a set of rules for describing APIs, including the available endpoints, the data models used by the API, the authentication methods, and more. This information can be used by clients to understand how to interact with the API and to generate code and documentation automatically.

One of the key benefits of using the OpenAPI specification is that it promotes consistency and reduces the amount of documentation that developers need to write. By providing a standardised way to describe APIs, it helps ensure that APIs are well-documented and easy to understand. Additionally, the OpenAPI specification allows for the automatic generation of client libraries, which can save developers a significant amount of time.

All documentation of the developed Universal Application Programming Interface is publicly available at the GitHub repository¹⁰. Following are some examples of the standard responses:

¹⁰<https://erigrd2.github.io/JRA-3.1-api/universal-api.html>

- *GET/info request*

```
{
  "id": "rwth",
  "transport":
  {
    "type": "villas-node",
    "version": "v0.12.0"
  }
}
```

Figure 13: uAPI response for GET/info.

- *GET/channels request*

```
[
  {
    "id": "DTU::Storage_Vanadium:M_EA_Watt.instMag",
    "description": "string",
    "payload": "events",
    "range":
    {
      "min": 0,
      "max": 0
    },
    "writable": true,
    "readable": true,
    "datatype": "float",
    "unit": "V",
    "rate": 0
  }
]
```

Figure 14: uAPI response for GET/channels.

4 Conclusions

This document reports the outcomes of the tasks that are focused on middleware development and data exchange, respectively. A generic software framework has been designed to further the development of a laboratory middleware which constitutes all shared services to enable seamless integration of RIs.

In particular, combining tools and knowledge from ERIGrid, a tool-agnostic uAPI has been developed to simplify and standardise joint multi-RI experiments. It provides a simplified interface for users to access and interact with other RIs. By using a common interface, the API eliminates the need for users to understand the complex and varied details of each individual RI. The uAPI has been designed to support a wide range of applications, including co-simulation and distributed laboratory experiments. The API can be easily integrated into existing simulation frameworks and is compatible with a variety of programming languages and operating systems.

A proof-of-concept of data exchange between multiple RIs using the developed uAPI was also undertaken. This demonstrated the middleware's ability to cover the required services for data exchange. The report also provides examples of implementation and associated documentation for the developed software tools, with links to the respective code repositories.

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